

Turning Socioecological Evidence into Multi Level Actions for Success in Preclinical Anatomy Examination

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What do we know?

Anatomy is a foundational course but **cognitively demanding** leading to varied success levels amongst students (Brenner, 2022)

A 5-year study of **four large-cohort** Nigerian medical schools reported **increased failure** in anatomy part 1 MBBS exam compared to physiology and human biochemistry (Obikili et al. 2006)

A decade analysis of a **single large-cohort** institution suggests **parity of outcomes** across the basic sciences (Iyawe & Ebojele, 2017)

Student outcomes reflect
interacting influences that
extend **beyond individual
study skills and personal
characteristics**

Learning **CONTEXT** matters in academic performance (Kassab et al., 2024)

Why do students fail anatomy?

Most academic performance initiatives **emphasize individual remediation** rather than the nested conditions in which learning and assessment occur (Cleland et al., 2013; Kalet et al., 2017).

There is dearth of studies holistically investigating the reasons medical students fail anatomy examination, especially using the **Socioecological Framework (SEF)** (Ellaway et al., 2017).

Study Objective

The socioecological framework (SEF) is designed to understand the complex interplay between individuals and their environments (Golden & Earp, 2012)

What we did

Results: SEF-Based Analysis

“... lectures (sic) was basically reading from a material... they didn't really teach anatomy... videos really helped me... classes did not help me.”

- Motivation
- Stress/Health
- Learning Resources/Difficulty
- Study Habits

“My mental health was in shambles... heart-wrenching experience; I withdrew for a few days.”

- Motivation
- Stress/Health
- Learning Resources/Difficulty
- Study Habits

“...can't study when I come back home because I will be stressed out”

- Motivation
- Stress/Health
- Learning Resources/Difficulty
- Study Habits

“Anatomy is bulky...my reading frequency wasn't really high because the course was scary... I would just open my book and go back and sleep...”

Motivation

Stress/Health

Learning Resources/Difficulty

Study Habits

“I think... I didn’t just prepare well... probably I wasn’t understanding well enough.”

Motivation

Stress/Health

Learning Resources/Difficulty

Study Habits

“I tried to join some study groups, but they were already full... I was on my own.”

Peer proximity and support

I stayed far from medicine students... If I was closer... it could have been better

Peer proximity and support

“...release quiz results before exams so everybody will know where they stand.”

- Large class size
- Limited access to models and/or cadavers
- Feedback lag
- Compressed calendars & assessment clustering
- OSCE/viva practice availability

“Most of the organs... I had never seen them before...”

Large class size

Limited access to models and/or cadavers

Feedback lag

Compressed calendars & assessment clustering

OSCE/viva practice availability

“That first steeplechase... my first time experiencing it... you ring the bell and start writing...”

Large class size

Limited access to models and/or cadavers

Feedback lag

Compressed calendars & assessment clustering

OSCE/viva practice availability

“We had only two cadavers for the whole class... dried up... crowded.”

- Large class size
- Limited access to models and/or cadavers
- Feedback lag
- Compressed calendars & assessment clustering
- OSCE/viva practice availability

“Sometimes... you’re at the back... you’ll not be getting what the lecturer is saying...”

Large class size

Limited access to models and/or cadavers

Feedback lag

Compressed calendars & assessment clustering

OSCE/viva practice availability

“Most of those equipment... we actually saw them during the exam period.”

- Large class size
- Limited access to models and/or cadavers
- Feedback lag
- Compressed calendars & assessment clustering
- OSCE/viva practice availability

“Back-to-back lectures...there should be time for recess during school hours... I can’t study when I come back home.”

- Large class size
- Limited access to models and/or cadavers
- Feedback lag
- Compressed calendars & assessment clustering
- OSCE/viva practice availability

'Sometimes no water or lights... unnecessary worry... decreased input in reading.'

Housing utilities and safety

Lack/proximity of community

Campus study rooms

“You wake up... first thing...
which water am I going to use...
phone I’m using to read...”

Housing utilities and safety

Lack/proximity of community

Campus study rooms

“My room was flooded... my books were soaked...” and later “somebody had broken into my room... everything was turned upside down.”

Housing utilities and safety

Lack/proximity of community

Campus study rooms

“I was literally alone in that lodge...”

Housing utilities and safety

Lack/proximity of community

Campus study rooms

“Mental health services are far from the College...”

- Assessment clustering & rigid deferral rules
- Strike actions
- Help-seeking stigma & pathways
- Quiz result delay
- Combined classes with other departments
- Late admissions/transfers

Strike... helpful in some aspects... covered some things... but... mental-health issues became full-blown.”

- Assessment clustering & rigid deferral rules
- Strike actions
- Help-seeking stigma & pathways
- Quiz result delay
- Combined classes with other departments
- Late admissions/transfers

“I didn’t join them to move directly after the time they did because I switched from zoology. So I joined them about four months later.”

Assessment clustering & rigid deferral rules

Strike actions

Help-seeking stigma & pathways

Quiz result delay

Combined classes with other departments

Late admissions/transfers

“Throughout the week we wrote our theory and MCQs I came down with... malaria... I had to be writing the exams with the malaria...”

Assessment clustering & rigid deferral rules

Strike actions

Help-seeking stigma & pathways

Quiz result delay

Combined classes with other departments

Late admissions/transfers

“Separate medicine students, even if you are separating both, separate them from medicine and... other departments... you guys require a lot more from us than you require from others...”

Assessment clustering & rigid deferral rules

Strike actions

Help-seeking stigma & pathways

Quiz result delay

Combined classes with other departments

Late admissions/transfers

SEF-Based Recommendations and Actors

Department/Institution
(Student Affairs)

- Micro coaching on study planning

Department

- Practice questions/Mock exams/practicals with feedback

Department

- Team-based learning
- Peer-mentoring

Department

- Section large practicals
- Medicine-only sessions
- Early exam/quiz result release
- Procure high-yield mannequins/models
- Faculty/Orientation/Medical education Workshop for Faculty
- Technology-based Learning Integration

Faculty/Tutors

- Align lectures/practicals to exam rubrics

Institution/Department

- Exam deferral protocol
- Daytime recess
- On-site mental-health access point

Department/Faculty
mentors

- Learning mentorship hours
- Late-entry/transfer onboarding make-ups

Study Implication

This multi level plan offers a practical pathway to improve student's performance, reduce avoidable stress, and strengthen a supportive learning culture.

Conclusions

Failure patterns in anatomy reflect systemic conditions, not “*anatomy exceptionalism*.”

Remediation practices that focus only on individuals miss the reality.

Student’s performance improves when we act across levels, not just on students.

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Thank you

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